

Towards General AI in view of The Human Problem

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Abstract. Genetic engineering, nanotechnology, robotics and general artificial intelligence or superintelligence have been named as a few likely routes toward a single, unified system described with heretofore unimaginable power. This paper summarizes a few of the topics from major publications of the millennium, including potential problems of a momentous nature depending on how future deployments of super technologies might progress. Given the expected near future development of one or some of these into super technologies compared with the low state or absence of cogent and authoritative planning, the various risks of militarization, abuse and or accidents arising from one of these or another super technology is estimated to exceed that of the risk posed by nuclear or other weapons of mass destruction of the previous century. A technology development approach is needed to renovate global human executive decision-making specifically to handle new threats to life which human technological development is implying.

Keywords: GNR, human evolution, strong AI, narrow AI, Singularity, social conflict theory, transhumanism

1. Introduction

In any of its numerous aspects the ultimate technology is under very active development and discussion by some of the world's best minds and foremost institutions as well as almost every university and tech company. It is variously referred to as general artificial intelligence, an intelligence explosion, the "Singularity" and others. Notwithstanding individual naming of the topic, its problems and peculiar emphases, it can be characterized as the summation of all human knowledge and information, scientific, engineering and medical progress on a path for coalescence into a single, unified system described with heretofore unimaginable power: practical omnipotence, omniscience and omnipresence. This paper adds little new but to attempt to increase and amplify the conversation about the near-future manmade existential crises which may result. For some of our contemporaries around the world in 2022, existential crisis could mean the competitive struggle to secure the largesses of the good life, obtainment of clean air and water, beating the pandemic COVID-19 or other disease, extending life expectancies, avoiding accidents or outlasting bombardment and siege. An intelligence explosion of the kind imaginable by linking up a good, working machine-learning program on an infinite feedback loop resulting in a technological Singularity either

promises to solve all the world's problems as we know them and thrust us into a gleaming and heavenly utopian future, or threatens a more complicated path that could quickly devolve into hellish cataclysm. These are interpretations of possible outcomes described by some of the foremost thinkers alive today, no mere catchy hyperboles. This paper examines some of the major publications and presentations defining this unique opportunity and terror, with special emphasis on what the author calls The Human Problem. As Bill Joy summed up, we "cannot solve a management problem with more technology" [1].

1.2 General artificial intelligence is a goal of global scientific endeavor. Although AI is work in progress, as it is developed and deployed, it becomes apparent that general AI impinges upon and draws from the full knowledge and resources of every other field. The implications are so far-reaching that it requires philosophers to reconsider the definition of concepts which are on the verge of extreme and rapid change, perhaps most notably the term "human." Exactly because it is the stated goal of an increasingly equipped global effort, the deployment of a general AI, a technical Singularity and more or less sudden transition from naturally evolved humanity into an actively designed and augmented post-humanity seems to be more a question of "when" than "if." For these and many more reasons it is still not too early to attempt a thorough discussion of the manifold resulting topics and ramifications. If the deployment of a general AI, along with or as a result of the many co-developing and concomitant information, nano-, bio-, medical and other technologies is just a matter of time, then discussions (and decisions) on how to bring that about safely and judiciously may be just in-time.

1.3 Deployment of such a total, unified (or Singularized) integrated system is already underway and in many ways it has been for a very long time. If however there is a moment that can be pinpointed, as a system suddenly coming "online" then the following discussion is vain. There will be nothing left to discuss after, if so. Previous large scale machines and their programs have taken some time to install, deploy and boot up, and such processes are not instantaneous but rather occur over time and, by definition at least, in a specific order. This view was supported by Paul Allen in [2]. A number of experts disagree whether any such Singularity is forthcoming or not in the relatively near future timeframe imagined by Kurzweil and others. Several papers have surveyed experts in AI to assess a general opinion of if or when a Singularity might occur. Grace et al. break the question down into milestones, asking world experts in the field of AI when AI can be expected to overtake human expertise in various settings. A simple majority expected total machine superiority in all fields by 2060 and a supermajority expected it only a decade or so later [3]. Korteling and van de Boer-Visschedijk et al. recently exclaimed that "Multiple narrow AI is most relevant now!" [4].

If a general, superintelligent system should come into existence in any way, preventing it from acting on its own agency cannot be expected. Any notions of control or defense against decisive superiority are futile. Short of this however, during the interim period when such a Singularity is booting up, whether on tracks of e.g. genetic engineering, nanotech and robotics (GNR), AI or others, this is where the dangers, and the final opportunities for defense are most critical.

2. Approach

The author surveys recent topics of interest in future studies and moves topically over a few major contemporary authors in the subjects mentioned (with an effort to stay in the more scientific, less fictional streams.) The outcomes of yet-to-be-deployed science is by definition speculative, but there are foreseeable problems on the near horizon which could and should receive urgent attention. Ostentatious predictions which stray into wishful thinking and fantasy have often been revealed by time to be so.

It bears mention that among two generally prevailing approaches, a “technology optimism” seems to pair with a popular science appeal, while the need for cautious deliberation and pessimism of a net positive outcome seems to prevail among philosophy departments and hard-er science sources. Notably excepted is Alvin Toffler’s percipient *Future Shock* [5] whose main thesis of the acceleration of change Kurzweil’s reiterates numerous times. While based on anthropological and sociological principles and written for a popular audience (over 6 million copies sold [6]) *Future Shock* was cautionary. Joy, Kurzweil, Bostrom and others offer particular attention to the transformative power and dangers arising from the fields of GNR and AI.

After the brief survey of the most prominent technological advances, the hoped-for results and some of the dangers that those capabilities could pose, the author makes this paper’s main point: Any proposed controls and defenses against spectacular self-injury to species and planet seem to be impossible absent the development of an authoritative and similarly advanced global executive power.

2.2 Attributes

Some attributes of the proposed advances, fully deployed in the world, would be:

Whole Brain Emulation “...to transcend [the] limitations of our biological bodies and brains” [7]. Taken to an extreme, this would lead to the ability to have whole brain emulation (WBE) also known as brain uploading [8]. WBE proposes to digitally master a person’s brain (presumably along with some better understanding of the mechanisms for consciousness, self-awareness, individual experiences, sensations, abilities, etc.) and have that saved into machine memory for use and editing, potentially for a very long time and without its original container. It hardly needs pointing out that such a possibility raises enormous moral questions, not the least of which being who or what would control such WBE uploaded information? While this strikes some as very far-fetched, in fact the Brain Connectome project, which has been underway in multiple laboratories since 2005, attempts to map the sum connective workings of the human brain. Some engineering work like Sporns’ [9], and some more epistemic or philosophical such as the (famously not-yet developed) theory of the mind are necessary steps. Compared to the human Genome Project, which mapped the entire human genetic code employing thousands of researchers’ input over a period of 10 years, the Connectome could be something like 100,000 times more complicated than the genome. “Simply” knowing all the possible axonal and dendritic connections and their average typical flows pre stimulus is almost certainly not sufficient for WBE, but

it is probably necessary. Again, with this type of work in progress, giant questions of "if" are rendered more and more to the realm of "when."

Ubiquity, Interfaces. Near future advances in robotics (especially as assisted by IoT and nanotechnologies) promise to provide more and more real time, real world interfaces to computers, whether under the direction of humans or their software, uploaded humans as agents in the machine, or as their own autonomous (and perhaps relatively soon to be, superior) beings. More and more actions will be possible from more locations with increasing precision and efficacy. Note the other term for ubiquity is omnipresence, and with all that data coming in from literally everywhere, it could be omnipresence leading the other two (omniscience and omnipotence) to the Singularity. It would be sufficient but not necessary for any one of the three to be actualized and the other two will soon follow.

Control over matter. "Nanotechnology promises to give us thorough control over the structure of matter" [10]. "Mature nanotechnology will transform manufacturing into a software problem. To build something, all you will need is a detailed design of the object you want to make and a sequence of instructions for its construction. Rare or expensive raw materials [will be] generally unnecessary..." [11].

Special longevity. The total triumph of medical technology over disease, aging and even death [Kurzweil p. 212]

Each of the above mentioned examples present obvious benefits and winners, but also acute moral dilemmas, potential economic and social changes which could destabilize the planet and its people in unprecedented fashion.

2.3 Risks

An abbreviated preview of the most obvious risks of the aforementioned would be:

Grey Goo. Demise by the so-named "grey goo" debacle: the event in which our machine creations enter into competition for resources of space, matter, and energy. Self-replicating nanobots or their seed data could be spread throughout the Internet of Things or some geographic portion of the physical world and proliferate greatly. Within a span of time too short for human defensive capabilities to be discussed, much less enacted, the nanobots consume all or enough of the earth's air, water, carbon or other elemental resources to end the lives of its biological competitors, including of course humans. Obviously this scenario need not be limited to nanobots per se, malice, programming errors or design flaws. Self-replication loops, given the right platforms and any one of the aforementioned mechanisms, will present a clear threat to be navigated [11]. The Grey Goo problem is not a new idea and though some defenses of varying imaginable effect have been proposed, once a grey goo debacle initiates, any post-facto discussions may be null, along with their very intelligent carbon life forms. The level of technology required to achieve the ability to enact a Grey Goo debacle may present more immediate global threats, however.

Bad Actors. (A) bad actor(s) could obtain militarized or militarize-able GNR technology of significantly greater power and ease of dispersion than that of nuclear weapons. Bill Joy [12] wrote:

“In truth, we have had in hand for years clear warnings of the dangers inherent in widespread knowledge of GNR technologies—of the possibility of knowledge alone enabling mass destruction. But these warnings haven’t been widely publicized; the public discussions have been clearly inadequate. There is no profit in publicizing the dangers.

The nuclear, biological, and chemical (NBC) technologies used in 20th-century weapons of mass destruction were and are largely military, developed in government laboratories. In sharp contrast, the 21st-century GNR technologies have clear commercial uses and are being developed almost exclusively by corporate enterprises.”

Studies of participating agents throughout history and in theoretical games show that there have been no “bad actors” in such a sense, only good actors who make mistakes and competitors who haven’t experienced need or opportunity to act badly, yet. (See also *The Human Problem*, below.) Even a very recent history of human civilization and the current state of affairs are far too rife with example to bother naming names, with ample blame for all parties to share generously.

Superintelligence. Together with GNR and general AI, or as a result of one or more of them, a superintelligent machine agent presents another great power and existential risk. A superintelligent agent is the ultimate human creation and stated goal of numerous designers, artists, inventors and scientists contemporary, passed and yet to come. As it comes to pass, it will be a thing of unimaginable beauty, power, terror or awe, speed and mystery. Infinite machine learning, or even just extremely fast and powerful machine-learning, combined with robot interfaces can provide the computer (or network) with a real-world, real-time presence and adaptability. In other words, omniscience and omnipresence would be achieved artificially, not by man but by his creation, and rather out of our control by the time of its fact. Some refer to such un-knowable and un-controllable (or partly knowable or controllable) factors as items in the umbra of an “event horizon” [7]. There is no way to defend or protect against any agent endowed with such power; however Bostrom does consider a number of possible ways in which forethought and planning might be used to prevent the machines from achieving such power [11]. Preventative “relinquishment” (choosing not to deploy or attempting to prohibit the most destructive capabilities of super technologies) may offer some stop-gap solution to the runaway advancement of an autonomous system (presumably until such point as human intelligence can develop better control or defenses from his creation) but any such attempts are sure to be temporary, if at all effective. Thus the last line of defense: mere hope that the superintelligent agent will choose to act benevolently, compassionately and altruistically toward us as its creators, and faith that it will do so.

Many discussions about what is a general AI, its state, its milestones or its future seem to dwell upon comparisons to human intelligence as a marker, or even as

some kind of goal, a pinnacle, a coda of achievement. Of course human-level machine intelligence will be none of those things, nor maybe even a recognizable signpost on AI's very speedy road to totality. Indeed it is very difficult to make comparisons between human and machine intelligence [4], though some have opined that we may be very near (whether past or soon to come) that threshold in terms of brute calculating power [13]. The "wet" animal hardware of human intelligence remains vastly superior in terms of energy requirements, heating and cooling efficiency. The distinction is not trivial considering the massive amounts of energy required to achieve the artificial version. (Recall the Grey Goo problem). Other fundamentals such as human electro-chemical versus the machines' light-speed transmission method strongly imply our systemic inferiority if not obsolescence. The pace and scale of AI development is such that, once prior "unsolvable" barriers begin to fall, others soon follow. It is also well-known that a top-level supercomputer race towards AI is on, that that race is highly nationalist, competitive and at least partly military in purpose [14].

Regardless of many discussions of the end of Moore's Law, advances in hardware speed continue to amaze. While more speed, more parallelization, deeper searches and bigger data add more power to the march toward machine superiority, AI is regarded mostly as a concern of software. An "organic" development of superintelligence could occur as the convergence of various systems, technologies and competencies under the control of a machine-learning regimen, but shortcuts based on what humans know of the nature of intelligence might speed that up. One shortcut goes something like this: First, figure out how what makes human brains so great, that is, develop an operating computational model of the human mind. As an aside this may seem at once an astoundingly vain and self-flattering notion, and yet full of overreach. Then, after developing a human brain-like algorithm, run that on the significantly faster, more powerful machine. Another, albeit much more costly pathway to superintelligence is through brute force [11], back-engineering the earth's collective historic genome looking for the path toward (e.g. human, but not necessarily) intelligence, and then accelerating the development of intelligence through genetic manipulation. These are ideas just waiting to happen--the energy requirement to run such a program is simply not available today but we should expect that once it is, it will.

3. Results

Extreme change demands caution. It is highly informative that strong words of caution have come from the founders and inventors of present computer systems. In his turn of the century open letter to the tech community in *Wired*, co-founder of Sun Microsystems and co-developer of the UNIX operating system Bill Joy published one of the most important articles of the generation. In it he spells out some of the unintended consequences of our scientific progress since the middle of WWII and outlines the history and philosophy of technological relinquishment [12].

Five years after Joy's article, Ray Kurzweil, now a director at Google, wrote that which has brought the most attention to the subject in recent years in a pop-sci-

ence format. It is framed in Kurzweil’s broad understanding of new information technologies in development with copious projections thereupon, most of which have not happened in the way or by the time which he conjectured. We eschew such specific predictions and their tendency to fail, or worse mislead, as possible futures become the vivid present. Yet it is important and perhaps essential to survival of species to acknowledge present trends, tendencies and likely outcomes. Even Kurzweil’s relative optimism acknowledges “deeply intertwined promise and peril of GNR” [Kurzweil, Chapter 8] and a “panoply of existential risks” [Kurzweil p. 400]. He adds that relinquishment of the most powerful and risk-heavy of technologies is not a realistic option, not necessarily because it may not be good, smart or perhaps greatly needed, but because of its impracticality. Kurzweil is among the *most* optimistic of current day tech giants.

4. Discussion

4.1 Human Time

Many have published much of the same information, drawn on similar charts to show the exponential growth of intelligence, change, technology and other phenomena.

Figure 1. The reader is likely to be well-acquainted with these parabolic expressions.

Let us also consider how little time on earth humans have contemplated their on-line profiles or congratulated themselves for owning an attractive Product Y, in contrast with the bulk of human time on earth, say pre-soap.

Figure 2. The stunningly swift development of more and more useful stuff is recent; a culmination of much slower and less glamorous progress e.g. from tree-dwelling hominids to hominids trudging the savannah or decisive primacy among cave mammals.

Perhaps the naturally-evolved genetic human that we are has not yet acclimated our general understanding or mastered group decision-making in our newly created social and technological entanglement.

4.2 Vanity

The concept of “modernity” in human evolution is very quaint and self-flattering. Consider the human condition 1.7 million years ago, 170,000, 17,000 and 1,700 years ago. Seeing as the oldest homo erectus fossils are roughly 1.7 million years old, and humans first touched their Earth's moon 54 years ago, the “modern era” “space age” “rocket age” “information age” is about 1/30,000 of the length of time since something that could be called a human descended from the hominid line [15]. The earliest appearance of manufactured pottery in the world is believed to have been almost 17,000 years ago [16] or older [17]. This period of human ingenuity starting somewhat post-language but perhaps prior to the advent of agriculture then represents an almost invisible 1% of their time on earth. One-tenth of that time ago, the people inhabiting islands which would come to be known as “Japan” were still enjoying their final pre-metallurgic civilization. It would be over 1,500 more years until the ostensible abolition of slavery in the United States. One level of magnitude later, this modern rocket age cannot fit even as a one-pixel thin line on the human time scale shown above. Now let us consider the change acceleration going the other direction in time 1.7×10 years, 1.7×10^2 , 1.7×10^3 or 1.7×10^4 years in the future. What will the future people say about us--will we seem “modern,” evidence-based or information-directed to our descendants? It is quite possible that if there are humans in 170 years, they will see early 21st century humans as being much closer to stone age pot makers than to the post-humans of the 22nd century. Given our collective dearth of information-age compassion for one another and apparent inability to assess and avert potentially mutually catastrophic events of our own doing, perhaps we have somehow become even more primitive than that.

4.3 The Human Problem

Whether or not the moniker is an accurate one, the Medieval Period or Dark Ages were so named for the perception of centuries of collapsed art, culture and civilization in Europe between the fall of the Roman Empire and the Renaissance. Maybe we are in a New Dark Age (or just still stuck in the old one), with large portions of the world under-fed, under-educated, under-represented and oft maligned, especially women [18], on this circus ride of civilization. In comparatively wealthy countries like the United States and Japan, a type of slavery continues quite normally, called wage slavery or working poverty.

It is deemed the responsible thing for anyone capable of doing so to assume power over others (lest that power come into less responsible competing hands). The principle is enshrined in the country's rise from the Monroe Doctrine and its corollaries, the embrace of R. Kipling's *The White Man's Burden* and the Potsdam Treaty, among numerous others. These cannot have escaped the aspirations and planning of the leaders of present day hegemonic hopefuls. Social Conflict theory appears to be in very smooth working order at the most macro-political-economic levels, more than any other principle or nation-actor. In this context, the prospects of increasingly powerful technologies prompted Russian President

Vladimir Putin to say that the nation which controls AI will rule the world--an amazingly candid and true warning, depending on the delineation of the term nation. That ruler need not be a state actor, and not necessarily beholden to any of the traditional mores or duties to constituents, land, agreements, understandings or systems of government. Though not yet a fact, it is logical that super-powerful machines would be able to re-program themselves into programs more suitable to their purpose, and that they will do so. Machine self-learning (and self-improvement, and self-reprogramming) will occur at first with but eventually without human control. That is, unless weak links in the chain of systems provide systemic collapse before full deployment.

4.4 Special Features of the Human Problem

- **Extreme self-interest**, combined with the will to deceive and self-deceive; only the most nascent forms of global leadership and planning, but deeply wrought with schisms of tribal misgivings
- **Profound vanity** and shortsightedness punctuated by only the most fleeting moments of forethought (forethought limited usually to months or years, but rarely decades and perhaps never centuries or longer)
- **Vicious, chronic** racial and class division, with coercive and often violent enforcement of divisions
- **Amazing powers** of self-destruction: war, pollution, nuclear weapons, nuclear power plants and their accidents, anthropogenic global warming
- **Rampant abuse** of public goods resulting in the destruction of the delicate homeostatic conditions which support life on Earth

Some problems have technological solutions but many are mired in decision making processes called “The Human Problem.” Some components of The Human Problem can be clearly seen in flux, improving in some states in leaps and bounds in the course of single lifetimes, but it seems evident that the pace of improvement in human technology (i.e. organization, decision-making, planning, economy, diplomacy, disaster response) will always lag a few to several cycles behind its business and technological improvements.

5. Conclusions

The likelihood of any of the mentioned scenarios of exponential advances in genetics, nanotech, robotics, or a “superintelligence explosion” arising from or leading to general AI, or a Singularity event, may be quite irrelevant. It is already apparent that human technology, even just in the form of good old fashioned nuclear power, is an existential threat and that the powers mentioned here are on the cusp of exponential improvements, hence exponential increases in the dangers they pose.

Relinquishment or de-militarization of some or any one of these likely superpowers appears to be increasingly futile as the stakes rise. Their deployment in the

present human civilization, mired in its Human Problem of incoherent executive leadership, planning, and agreement presents some clearly predictable and potentially existential risks as well as a few we can almost certainly not yet imagine.

Advance preparation for the control of and defending from potential existential risks arising from not-yet extant technological superpowers appears to be an excellent, very necessary, and perhaps only road to human species survival. After that time, humans (or transhumans or posthumans) will be powerless to control, much less to oppose machine-based agents which learn and act in the real world in real time (but at thousands of times faster than humans, and without need for sleep). The most critical conditions ripe for some major or total catastrophe arising out of human, or humans' machines' technological development occur between the present and that time when machines become smarter and stronger than the humans who have made them.

Furthermore, it is proposed that heretofore global planning, decision making and control regimes have themselves varied between the inadequate, such as in the form of gross inequalities, to the disastrous, such as in war, abuses of common goods, and grand "accidents" (which are rarely anything but accidents of good judgement). This decision-making environment is called The Human Problem. Although by many other names it has heretofore received much attention from the philosophers, advances have paled in comparison to the other technologies. The very technologies requiring cogent planning and unity of executive decision, namely GNR and AI, are being very well tended-to. It is quite possible that without great leaps of technological improvement in species-wide decision-making, the inherent risks of our technology will grow into our collective undoing.

References

1. Joy, B., What I'm Worried About, What I'm Excited About, Feb. 2006 [Online video]. Available: https://www.ted.com/talks/bill_joy_what_i_m_worried_about_what_i_m_excited_about?language=en
2. Allen, P., Graves, M., The Singularity Isn't Near, MIT Technology Review, 11 Oct., 2011.
3. Grace, K., Salvatier, J., Dafoe, A., Zhang, B., Evans, O., "Viewpoint: When will AI exceed human performance? Evidence from AI experts," *Journal of Artificial Intelligence Review*, 62:729-754, Jul. 2018.
4. Korteling, J.E.H., van de Boer-Visschedijk, G. C., Blankendaal, R.A.M., Boonekamp, R.C., Eikelboom, A.R., "Human- versus artificial intelligence," *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence* 4, Mar. 2021. Available: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/frai.2021.622364/full>
5. Toffler, A., *Future Shock*, Bantam Books, New York (1970). ISBN 0-553-27737-5
6. Wikipedia, Future Shock, accessed 18 Mar. 2022, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Future_Shock
7. Kurzweil, R., *The Singularity is Near*, Penguin Books, New York (2005).
8. Sandberg, A., Bostrom, N., Technical Report #2008-3, Whole Brain Emulation: A Roadmap, Future of Humanity Institute, Oxford University <https://www.fhi.ox.ac.uk/reports/2008-3.pdf>
9. Sporns, O., *Networks of the Brain*, MIT Press, Boston (2011).
10. Transhumanist FAQ, Version 3.0, What is Transhumanism? [Online]. Accessed: Mar. 23, 2022. Available: <https://whatistranshumanism.org/#about>
11. Bostrom, N., *Superintelligence, Paths, Dangers, Strategies*, Oxford University Press, New York (2014).
12. Joy, B., Why the future doesn't need us, *Wired*, Apr. 1, 2000.

13. Ma, Z., He, J., Qiu, J., Cao, H., Wang, Y., Sun, Z., et al. "BaGuaLu: targeting brain scale pretrained models with over 37 million cores," in ACM SIGPLAN Annual Symposium on Principles and Practice of Parallel Programming (2022).
14. Anonymous Staff, "Japan's Fugaku keeps position as world's fastest supercomputer," Nikkei Asia, Jun., 2021. Available: <https://asia.nikkei.com/Business/Technology/Japan-s-Fugaku-keeps-position-as-world-s-fastest-supercomputer>
15. Britannica, Homo Erectus [Online]. Accessed: 23 Mar. 2022. Available: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Homo-erectus>
16. C. Violatti, World History Encyclopedia, Pottery in Antiquity [Online]. Accessed: 24 Mar. 2022. Available: <https://www.worldhistory.org/pottery/>, accessed 23 Mar. 2022.
17. Wu, X., Zhang, C., Goddard, P., Cohen, D., Pan, Y., Arpin, T., Bar-Yosef, O., Early pottery at 20,000 years ago in Xianrendong Cave, China, Science Vol. 336 No. 6089, 2012. doi 10.1126/science.1218643
18. Sirgy, M., Estes, R., Selian, A., "How we measure well-being: The data behind the history of well-being," in *The Pursuit of Human Well-Being-The Untold Human History*, pp. 135-157, Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature (2017).
19. "Where Your Income Tax Really Goes FY 2022" (PDF) The War Resisters' League, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.warresisters.org/store/where-your-income-tax-money-really-goes-fy2022>
20. TED Conferences LLC, J. Enriquez, We Can Reprogram Life; How to Do it Wisely, Nov. 2015 [Online video]. Accessed: 26 Mar. 2022. Available: https://www.ted.com/talks/juan_enriquez_we_can_reprogram_life_how_to_do_it_wisely?language=en
21. Sandberg, A., "The greatest long-term threats facing humanity," BBC Future 19 Jul. 2019. Accessed: 19 Mar. 2022. Available: <https://www.bbc.com/future/article/20190719-the-greatest-long-term-threats-facing-humanity>